

Blockchain-based Self-Sovereign Identity Solution for Aerial Base Station Integrated Networks

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Abstract

Identity and access management frameworks address user access rights and data governance for organizations, vendors and users. In response to the problems associated with centralized authorities (e.g. single point of failure, limited scalability, lack of user control), new identity management models have emerged, such as Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI), which relies on verifiable data registers to validate Decentralized Identifier (DIDs) and can be achieved in many different ways, e.g. through Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), distributed databases or other decentralized systems. The main goal of SSI is to enable users to take control of managing their data shared with different services. In this paper, we examine a possible application of the SSI concept to aerial base station (ABS)-integrated networks. The paper presents the effective use of DID implementation to provide a secure and decentralized way to create, associate and verify credentials and identities of ABSs, ensuring secure communication between Ground Base stations (GBSs) and other nodes in the network in a multi-operator scenario. In the numerical results, the average values of various metrics (namely, the average credential presentation time, the average credential offer time, the average DIDcomm connection creation time, the average DIDcomm signing time, and the average DIDcomm revoke credential time) related to credential operations in a DID management system are given for three different number of requests (50K, 75K, and 100K). We have also provided the values of the different status codes that occurred in 100K operations in the same DID management system. Towards the end of the paper, a comparison is made between SSI-based and Non-fungible token (NFT)-based blockchain solutions, also discussing the challenges and future directions of SSI solutions in the context of ABS-integrated networks.

Keywords: self-sovereign identity, blockchain, authentication, security.

1. Introduction

As the number of devices used in the network infrastructure to access a variety of services increases, e.g. in smart cities with ubiquitous devices [1], it becomes increasingly difficult for

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service providers to accurately identify and authenticate devices for specific services. With the growing number of devices, operators and service providers are facing new challenges in terms of security and privacy within cellular networks [2, 3]. Even though 5G has mature identification and authentication techniques and is designed for Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC) scenarios, it is still possible that complementary techniques to existing authentication mechanisms in 5G are needed to overcome certain challenges or improve security and privacy aspects, especially in scenarios with a large number of devices where traditional centralized approaches may reach their limits. Virtually all web-based applications that currently exist on the Internet rely on digital identity services to function effectively. However, most of the user identity and access management systems available today rely on single sign-on solutions and multi-factor authentication methods, which in turn can introduce additional risks to the overall trustworthiness of the systems, including but not limited to identity theft and fraudulent users, as they often operate on centralized platforms.

In the context of Aerial Base Station (ABS)-integrated within multi-operator networks, there is a need for robust and secure identity management solutions. The challenge arises from the dynamic and distributed nature of ABS operations, which require effective authentication, authorization and information sharing between ABS and Ground Base Stations (GBSs). Traditional identity systems (typically with centralized databases or directories managed by a trusted authority, such as a government agency, employer or service provider) may not be able to meet the unique requirements of ABS-integrated networks (such as scalability, dynamic & mobile environments, decentralized nature at scale, diverse ecosystems or adaptation to emerging technologies, e.g., blockchain), especially in scenarios where trust, accountability and privacy are paramount. Therefore, a novel and adaptable identity management solution is sought to ensure secure interactions, traceability and trustworthiness between different entities in disaster response and other critical contexts. A novel digital identity model has emerged, known as Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI). This model is based on the integration of Blockchain Networks (BCNs) technology, alongside advances in cloud computing and mobile technologies [4]. SSI can also help to promote transparency and trust [5]. For example, during the process of sharing data, individuals can make informed decisions about sharing their data with others to ensure privacy and security. One of the most important principles of SSI is to ensure that only the information necessary for a service is collected. Sharing partial digital identities for each service can also help to prevent re-identification and correlation of data. In parallel, next-generation Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR) applications in ABS-integrated networks must utilise advanced registration mechanisms to enhance security and privacy, including authentication. As ABSs move through different regions (either within a country or between countries), a true mobility system must support advanced authentication methods [6, 7]. In multi-operator situations, roaming procedures between operators for shared GBSs and ABS authentication, integrity and confidentiality of ABS data must be ensured. In this paper, we develop a secure, efficient and adaptable identity management solution specifically tailored for ABS integrated in multi-operator networks. Our intention is to overcome the challenges of authentication, authorization and information sharing that are typical to ABS, ultimately contributing to more effective disaster response and critical communication scenarios.

1.1. Related Work

ABS-assisted PPDR scenario: As reported in recent studies [8], the popularity of ABSs for the purpose of PPDR efforts has increased significantly. These systems typically use Base Stations (BSs), which are usually mounted on Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) or drones and can be quickly deployed in areas affected by natural disasters or other emergencies e.g., surveillance and

epidemic prevention as in [9] to ensure that vital connectivity is maintained. In the area of ABS-integrated networks, there are also projects supported by H2020 to develop applications such as PPDR. “5G!Drones” project¹ trials several UAVs use-cases, covering Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC) and mMTC 5G services. Primo-5G² demonstrates an end-to-end 5G system that provides immersive video services for moving objects. However, despite numerous advantages with ABS-integrated networks, there are still a number of problems that need to be solved. These include concerns about security, data collection and the potential misuse of this technology. Note also that ABSs themselves have inherent security risks and vulnerabilities that must be carefully considered and appropriate measures taken to ensure their integrity and confidentiality. Some of the threat models in this area are identity spoofing and the unauthorized presentation of credentials, for which the implementation of an SSI with blockchain technology as in this paper can be a solution. Although the ABS-assisted PPDR scenario may not involve a large number of devices compared to the usual use cases, it should be borne in mind that the number of networked devices in the various industries is continuously increasing. This could lead to scenarios where even less common applications such as ABS-assisted PPDR could experience significant device growth over time.

BCNs for ABS integrated networks: The use of BCN to create transactions based on interactions between nodes has been studied in many relevant areas of telecommunication networks [10]. In ABS-integrated networks, ABS-integrated data such as Global Positioning System (GPS) coordinates, altitude and speed together with network-related information such as signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR), Channel Quality Indicator (CQI), throughput and Bit Error Rate (BER), etc, [11] can also be committed to BCN as transactions (similar to, e.g. the service orchestration logs committed to BCNs in [10]). Recent advances and the widespread adoption of blockchain technology [12] have also facilitated the authentication of users through BCNs. In [3], a cloud-based authentication system that uses blockchain technology for Internet of Things (IoT) devices is investigated. In addition, it was shown in [2] that a blockchain-based authentication system can reduce communication latency compared to existing protocols for 5G-enabled IoT. While it is also true that blockchains involve some computational overhead [13] (e.g. due to their consensus mechanisms), it is important to recognize that in cases where security, trust and data integrity are of paramount importance, the trade-off of slightly lower efficiency may be justified. In addition, ongoing research and development efforts in blockchain technology are actively addressing performance issues, which could alleviate concerns about efficiency.

Authentication: While it’s true that 5G has made significant advances in security, including the adoption of mutual authentication between user equipments (UEs) and BSs, it’s important to consider that security threats are constantly evolving and attackers often adapt their strategies to exploit vulnerabilities in the latest technologies. False Base Stations (FBSs) in mobile networks is an important concern for Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) [14, 15]. A FBS is a type of device that can impersonate a legitimate base station in a wireless communication network. Fake BSs can be used to intercept, manipulate or steal sensitive information, including user credentials and identity information. There are several issues related to signal interference, encryption, privacy, liability (for false alarms), transparency and authentication when detecting false BSs. In addition, the deployment of ABSs brings new complexities. These aerial units might operate in environments where physical security is harder to ensure, making them potentially more vulnerable to tampering

¹Online: <https://5gdrones.eu/>, Available: March 2023

²Online: <https://primo-5g.eu/>, Available: March 2023

or unauthorized access. International Mobile Subscriber Identity (IMSI) Catcher can also be a major problem and pose a significant threat to the privacy and security of mobile users. At the same time, there are several ways to prevent its effects, as outlined in [16]. In [6], a secure and lightweight authentication scheme is presented for an aerial network with multiple UAVs. A secure authentication scheme is provided in [7] to enable users and drones to authenticate each other and share a session key. In such scenarios, leveraging recent advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven security algorithms and BCNs for decentralized security can optimize the management of ABS-integrated cellular networks, with a focus on ensuring legitimate access to communication resources. A multi-layered security approach that includes BCN-based solutions could provide an additional layer of protection against emerging threats and ensure the highest level of security and trust in ABS operations. Note that while large-scale authentication issues are not a common scenario in ABS-supported PPDR, it is important to recognize that innovative solutions can still benefit from improved authentication processes in such scenarios, especially considering the potentially life-saving impact of PPDR operations.

BCN-based SSI: The use of BCN in a ABS- assisted PPDR scenario may not be immediately intuitive, but BCNs has proven to offer unique benefits that go beyond the usual authentication approaches. Blockchain’s ability to provide tamper-proof records, traceability and decentralized control could be used to improve the security, accountability and transparency of authentication processes, even in special scenarios such as PPDR. For instance, the blockchain’s data integrity and auditability features could help maintain accurate and reliable records in situations where ensuring the authenticity of actions is of paramount importance. There have been some attempts to develop BCN-based SSI systems for different domains [17, 18, 19, 20, 21]. A public blockchain-based system is proposed in [22] in the context of the European Union (EU) General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) and European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) are collaborating to define requirements for remote identity proof³. Verifiable credentials and Decentralized identifiers (DIDs) have been described in the W3C standards [23]. The OpenID foundation⁴ enables, protects, and promotes OpenID technologies. Decentralized Identity Foundation (DIF) develops an open ecosystem for DID and ensures interoperability [24]. The implementation of BCN-based decentralized identity solutions is growing rapidly. Zebra is the first zkSNARK-based anonymous credential for on-chain verification [25]. A permissionless decentralized digitized passport is implemented in [26]. The security and privacy of user identities and credentials compromised by fake BSs could potentially be avoided by using the used of DID implementation as a potential solution. DID protocols (e.g. used by Hyperledger Indy) can ensure that the identities and credentials are cryptographically protected and prevent unauthorized access or tampering of the information. This can provide network operators and service providers with strong security and privacy guarantees.

1.2. Our Contributions

Scalable and resilient authentication of ABS is still an ongoing process and not well studied as a use case. Furthermore, the desired level of confidentiality, authentication and integrity is still an ongoing research process. Most of the approaches listed above lack self-sovereign identity-based authentication of ABSs and their integration into multi-operator networks in their approach. To

³<https://www.etsi.org/newsroom/news/2067-2022-05-enisa-and-etsi-joint-workshop-tackles-challenges-for-european-identity-proofing>

⁴<https://openid.net/>

address the above issues, we propose a blockchain-based SSI technology for ABS-integrated networks, where the ability to securely manage identities and credentials, together with the provision of verifiable traceability, creates a new layer of security and accountability. The key innovations in this paper are the use of blockchain-based SSI technology for identity management in ABS-integrated networks, which brings the benefits of decentralization, data integrity and user control to the realm of ABS operations, the adaptation of blockchain-based SSI to the unique context of ABSs to address the challenges of dynamically moving ABSs, multi-operator networks and disaster response scenarios, build trust between ABS, GBSs and other entities in a decentralized manner to improve security and trustworthiness in a distributed environment, provide more granular identity control over identity attributes and information sharing compared to traditional solutions, and provide a comparative analysis between SSI and alternative solutions (such as Non-Fungible Token (NFT)-based approaches). Main contributions of this paper are listed as follows:

- A new architecture to enable a blockchain-based SSI framework is proposed for ABS-integrated networks in multi-operator cases for decentralized trust between MNOs in a ABS- assisted PPDR scenario.
- Various system level metrics are proposed and extensive simulation results are performed to obtain average values of various Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to credential operations in a Distributed Identity Management (DIM) system for three different scenarios, each with a different number of requests.
- SSI-based and NFT-based solutions are compared to enable authentication services for ABS-integrated networks, and challenges and future directions of BCN-based SSI solutions in ABS-integrated networks are presented.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides the system model and concepts, architecture and components of the paper. Section 3 gives the BCN-based SSI system for ABS-integrated networks and other relevant key control elements and data format. Section 4 gives the experimental setup and numerical results for the implemented DID system. Section 5 presents the challenges and possible future implementations. Section 4 gives the conclusion remarks.

2. System Model, Architecture and Components

In this section, we introduce the system architecture, components and model of the paper, present some metrics related to BCN-based authentication and provide some general background information for ABS identity management.

2.1. System Architecture

In a multi-operator scenario, it is important to build trust between different operators to enable seamless handovers and roaming, e.g. in PPDR scenarios. This can be achieved by using the BCN-based SSI architecture to create a trust framework that allows operators to securely exchange information and authenticate each other's devices. Fig. 1 shows the BCN-based SSI architecture and the interactions of the ABS with different GBSs belonging to different operators. This architecture is designed to address the challenges of identity management in multi-operator networks that integrate ABS. It consists of two layers: SSI management level and infrastructure level. At the SSI management level, there are entities such as the legal authority, the identity holder of ABS, the issuer and SSI BCN, and at the infrastructure level there are GBSs (belonging to multi-operators) and ABS.

Figure 1: BCN-based SSI architecture and interactions of moving ABS with different base stations in a multi-operator scenario to provide PPDR service.

2.2. Components of the Architecture

(i) Legal Authority: This entity establishes the legal framework and guidelines for identity management within the network. It defines the rules and standards that govern identity issuance, verification, and interactions. **(ii) Identity Holder of ABS:** This represents the Aerial Base Station itself, which holds its unique identity credentials and attributes. It can autonomously manage and selectively share these credentials for interactions with other entities. **(iii) Issuer:** The issuer entity generates and provides digital credentials to the ABS for identity verification. These credentials are based on blockchain technology, ensuring security and immutability. **(iv) SSI BCN:** This is the underlying blockchain infrastructure that forms the basis of the SSI system. It securely records and manages identity-related transactions, credentials, and interactions. **(v) GBSs:** These are entities belonging to different network operators. GBS plays the role of interacting with ABS for various purposes, such as requesting identity verification or communication setup.

2.3. Cheating Rates as a Basic Metric

Our main intent in this section is to evaluate one of the used metrics known as the Successful Cheating Rates (SCR) [27] of a given UE when a blockchain-based authentication mechanism is used during the cell selection phase. We follow the system model in which M legitimate BSs and a single FBS are present to communicate with an UE through orthogonal signalling. It is typical to use SCR as the probability that a given UE will connect to the false BS. In current cellular networks, if there is no established authentication mechanism, UEs search for the strongest synchronization signal [28] and hence could easily be a victim by the wisely adjusted power of a fake BS. If we let S_i to be average received synchronization signal strength for the i -th BS out of $M + 1$ base stations operationalized over L different time slots, the SCR can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{P}_S = \mathcal{P}(S_{FBS} > \max_{1 \leq i \leq M} S_i) \quad (1)$$

$$= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_{FBS}(x) \prod_{m=1}^M F_m(x) dx \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{P} is the probability measure, $f_i(x)$ and $F_i(x)$ are the probability density and distribution functions of S_i for $i \in \mathcal{S}_M \cup \{FBS\}$ where $\mathcal{S}_M := \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$. One simplifying assumption about the statistics of S_i s is given in [29], namely for large L , we have $S_i \sim \mathcal{N}(u_i, \sigma_h^2)$, where $u_i = \text{lt}(\sigma_h^2 P_i) - \alpha \text{lt}(d_i) - \gamma$ with $\text{lt}(x) = 10 \log_{10}(x)$ and γ being the Euler's constant. Moreover, σ_h^2 is the variance of the Rayleigh small scale fading factor, P_i is the transmit power of the i -th BS, α is the exponential factor of the path loss and d_i is the transmission distance. One striking observation is that for large enough $S_{FBS} - S_i$, $\mathcal{P}_S \rightarrow 1$, which implies the undesirable outcome that the UE almost always chooses to connect to the FBS. The general logic is to identify FBS through anomaly detection i.e., the one BS that clearly shows higher power level of operations. To keep the error level under certain threshold δ , satisfying $0 < \delta \leq 1$, one can define \bar{S}_M such that

$$\mathcal{P}\{\max_{1 \leq i \leq M} S_i > \bar{S}_M\} \leq \delta. \quad (3)$$

Thus, the anomaly region $\mathcal{I} = (\bar{S}_M, +\infty)$ shall define all BS that could potentially be a FBS. The UE in this case attempt synchronizing with the strongest power level available in $\mathcal{S}_M - \mathcal{I}$.

2.4. Analysis for Blockchain-Based Authentication

By implementing an authentication scheme, we can show that legitimate base stations can increase their chances of reducing cheating rates. This would be achieved by ensuring that UE searches for and connects to the strongest synchronization signal only if the underlying authentication process has been successfully completed by the base station. If we let the probability of any BS to fail in the authentication process be δ_A , and assume that UE always connects to an authenticated FBS if $\max_{1 \leq i \leq M} S_i > \bar{S}_k$, then the SCR can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{P}_S = \mathcal{P}(S_{FBS} > \max_{1 \leq i \leq M} S_i) \quad (4)$$

$$\approx \mathcal{P}(\max_{1 \leq i \leq M} S_i > \bar{S}_k)$$

$$= \sum_k \binom{M}{k} (1 - \delta_A)^k \delta_A^{M-k} \mathcal{P}\{\max_{i \in \mathcal{S}_k} S_i > \bar{S}_k\} \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{S}_k is the set of available and verified synchronization signal sources. With an increase in the number of authentic blockchain transactions, it is typical to expect a decrease in the rate of authentication failures within the system. This is due to the involvement of more trusted parties, which makes it increasingly difficult for fake identities and privacy breaches to occur. Although it is hard to model this relationship, for tractability we shall assume the Poisson approximation. Thus, as $M \rightarrow \infty$, we expect $\delta_A \rightarrow 0$ such that $M\delta_A$ is a constant. Eventually, SCR can be re-expressed as

$$\mathcal{P}_S \approx \sum_k \frac{e^{-M\delta_A} (M\delta_A)^k}{k!} \left[1 - \prod_{i \in \mathcal{S}_k} Q\left(\frac{u_i - \bar{S}_k}{\sigma_S}\right) \right] \quad (6)$$

where we have used the identity $Q(-x) = 1 - Q(x)$ for the Gaussian Q (error) function. As can be easily seen in (6), increase in the number of authenticated parties actually helps with the cheating rates. To clarify, let us posit that the j -th base station (BS) is in closer proximity to the user equipment (UE) compared to all other base stations. In the event that this nearby base station undergoes successful authentication, we would have

$$\mathcal{P}_{S|A} = \mathcal{P}(\max_{1 \leq i \leq M} S_i > \bar{S}) \approx \mathcal{P}(S_j > \bar{S}) = Q\left(\frac{\bar{S} - u_j}{\sigma_S}\right) \quad (7)$$

from which we obtain $\mathcal{P}_S = (1 - \delta_A)Q\left(\frac{\bar{S} - u_j}{\sigma_S}\right)$. This also implies that $\bar{S} \approx \sigma_A Q^{-1}\left(\frac{\delta}{1 - \delta_A}\right) + u_j$, demonstrating that false alarm rate can be reduced with better authentication schemes i.e., through ensuring smaller δ_A s.

After conducting a preliminary analysis, it has become evident that blockchain-based authentication schemes possess the potential to effectively minimize false alarm rates and hence can serve as a potential solution to the increasing problem of fake base stations. The implementation of such schemes on the other hand will offer a variety of design choices, which can help mitigate the risk of unauthorized access to mobile networks. By leveraging the inherent characteristics of blockchain technology, such as decentralization, transparency, and immutability, these authentication schemes can be demonstrated to provide an additional layer of security through following similar steps of analysis.

2.5. Key Control Points for ABS Identity Management

Identity management modeling has evolved from the simplest model to newer models [30]. In the traditional *centralized identity*, the user is authenticated separately for multiple applications and services. This is the most commonly used model today, which poses high security and privacy risks due to multiple copies of the data in the databases of service providers. In the case of *federated identity*, the user is authenticated only once with the identity provider (with only one set of credentials) and redirected to access different applications and services of service providers. Although the federated identity approach simplifies the user experience, it still carries risks as it requires a trusted identity provider. In SSI, the user is authenticated in applications via BCNs by using verifiable credentials (obtained directly from the credential issuers in the form of a cryptographic hash of the transaction) that can be selectively disclosed by users. Compared to Web 2.0, in Web 3.0 users control data usage without relying on centralized control or an intermediary. Three important control points are available for this comparison, which are described as follows.

- (i) **Decentralized Identity:** Attributes and identifiers are used to identify an individual or object in a specific role or context. This is for identities to access resources and a fundamental building block of a decentralized Public Key Infrastructure (PKI). In DID there is no central authority or certified registry. Instead, a Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) or BCNs are used to verify the information. DID can refer to any subject, such as a person, ABS, an organization, a data model, etc. In SSI-based systems, DIDs represent the cryptographically verifiable credential issued by authorities and stored in BCNs. In addition to holding the basic identity of ABS node, SSI can be used to verify any identity-related information or potential other types of information needed for transactions, such as for assessing risks, performing compliance checks, checking insurance status or ABS device health data.
- (ii) **Decentralized Access Control:** This approach is employed for data access control. In this methodology, user authentication occurs automatically, eliminating the need for reliance on centralized servers possessing substantial trust and authority to enforce access. The primary mechanism employed involves the segregation of authorization and access through the implementation of access policies and the controlled dissemination of secrets. Consequently, the processes of authorization and access are collaboratively designed. By possessing the identity's private keys, a ABS may demonstrate its authority over the identity. The DLT is used as a policy decision point to authorize data consumers via immutable transactions. After the approval of data access from BCN, the data consumer only receives the decryption key. Some key applications are policy-based data sharing between organizations, multiple application access to user consent data, managing access to IoT devices and systems, manage and tracking access to critical resources and information.
- (iii) **Decentralized Computation (policy-compliant):** This is used for data usage control and the computation of data without a central authority. The computation of data is performed in a way that conforms to a specific set of rules or policies. With this technique, computation is performed in a more secure, private, fair and transparent way. A prominent example is secure multi-party computation with verifiable secret sharing schemes, [31] in which an external blockchain is used to control the network, manage identities and access controls, and act as a tamper-proof log of events.

3. Self-Sovereign Identity Platform for ABS-Integrated Networks

3.1. Security properties of BCN-based SSI for ABSs

The security features of integrating ABS with BCN-based SSI ensure a comprehensive approach to securing the identity management system in the context of aerial base stations that meets the unique challenges and requirements of this scenario. Some of these features are listed as follows: **(i) Confidentiality of ABS data:** Ensure that sensitive information related to ABS, such as operating parameters and location data, is kept confidential and accessible only to authorized entities. **(ii) Integrity of ABS identities and certificates:** Guarantee the unaltered and accurate representation of ABS identities and associated credentials in the blockchain and prevent unauthorized modifications. **(iii) Authentication of ABS entities:** Verify the identity of ABS entities participating in the network to prevent identity spoofing and ensure that each ABS entity is uniquely and securely identified. **(iv) Authorization for ABS operations:** Control access to ABS-specific operations and resources based on permissions granted via the SSI system and ensure that only authorized entities can perform certain actions. **(v) Non-repudiation of ABS transactions:** Introduce a mechanism to prove that transactions or communications involving ABS entities have taken place to prevent their involvement in certain activities from being challenged. **(vi) Availability of ABS services:** Ensure that ABS services, including communications and identity verification, remain available even in the event of network disruptions or attacks. **(vii) Resilience against attacks on ABS identities:** Develop resilience mechanisms to recover from potential attacks or compromises targeting ABS identities stored on the blockchain. **(viii) Privacy preservation for ABS sites:** Implement privacy preservation techniques to protect the confidentiality of ABS sites while enabling secure communication and authentication. **(ix) Unavoidability of security measures:** Design security measures, including cryptographic controls, to prevent unauthorized entities from circumventing ABS-specific security measures. **(x) Least privilege for ABS entities:** Grant ABS entities the minimum level of access and permissions required for their specific roles, limiting potential risks associated with compromised identities. **(xi) Accountability for ABS actions:** Establish clear accountability for the actions performed by ABS entities within the network and enable tracking and auditing of their activities. **(xii) Auditability of ABS-BCN interactions:** Enable comprehensive logging and monitoring of interactions between ABS and the blockchain-based SSI system for auditing, analysis and compliance reporting.

3.2. Collaboration For Identity Management

The entities defined in Section 2 interact with each other based on the established identity and communication protocols. At the heart of this architecture is the idea of SSI, which allows entities such as ABS to have control over their own identity. The components collaborate to solve the identity problem as follows: **For the issuance and management of identities**, the legal authority establishes the rules and legal framework for identity management. The identity holder of ABS generates its unique identity credentials, which are securely stored within the BCN-based SSI system. The Issuer entity verifies the identity of ABS and issues digital credentials. **For authentication and interactions**, if a GBS (belonging to any operator) needs to interact with a ABS, the GBS can request an identity verification. The ABS provides its digital credentials to the requesting GBS. These credentials are cryptographically secured and can be verified via the BCN-based SSI. The GBS can trust the credentials provided by ABS and establish a secure communication channel or perform other authorized actions. **For transparency and traceability**, all interactions, including

identity requests, verifications and communication setups, are recorded in the SSI BCN. This general ledger ensures transparency, accountability and traceability of all identity-related transactions. **For autonomous control**, the ABS retains control over its own identity data and credentials. It can selectively share only the necessary information with authorized entities, while maintaining privacy and security.

3.3. Steps of interactions

The steps of a high-level overview of how a BCN-based SSI architecture can be used to facilitate interactions between a moving ABS and different GBSs in a multi-operator scenario are as follows: First, a digital identity for the ABS is created by the issuer using the BCN-based SSI network to enable secure and decentralized authentication and authorization. These identities are linked to the respective physical ABS and contain relevant metadata such as digital ID, owner, issue date, capabilities and access rights. This is shown in step- 1 and step- 2 of Fig. 1. To enable seamless handover and roaming between GBSs belonging to different operators without interruption of service, the SSI architecture is used to securely authenticate the ABS and establish a new connection with the new GBS, as shown in steps- 3 and 4 of Fig.1. Finally, to enhance the security of the system, the legal authority could have the authority to check the identity status of ABS, as shown in step- 5 of Fig. 1.

3.4. Data Format of the ABS Digital Identity

In this section, we present an example of a digital identifier format. Note that if ABS ownership or any of the related features changes, only that attribute will be updated. There is no need to create and register a new digital identity from scratch. A sample ABS identity can be as follows:

```
{
  Digital_id: "Value(hex)",
  Owner_MNO_Id: "Text",
  Owner_MNO_Type: "Private/Public",
  Issue_Date: "Date",
  Issuer: "Value",
  Did_Items: [
    {ABS_Type: "Text"},
    {ABS_Model: "Text"},
    {Colour: "Value"},
    {Frequencies: "Value"},
    {Duplex_Mode: "Value"},
    {Carrier_Agg: "Yes/No"}
    {Enable_RAN_Sharing: "Yes/No"}
    {PLMN_IDs: "Value"}
  ]
}
```

3.5. ABS Authentication with SSI Blockchain

Fig. 2 shows the proposed steps of BCN-based SSI for ABS authentication that is built on top of regular UAV authentication scheme [32], [33] that relies on of the The 3rd Generation Partnership

Project (3GPP) TR 33.854 Rel-17 standard which deals with security issues of Unmanned Aerial Systems (UASs)/UAVs. In comparison to 3GPP standard, only single identification number is assigned to a ABS by the UAS service provider and the 3GPP core network which is based on DID system. In this new flow diagram, SSI-BCN is used for taking some of the functionalities of traditional Unified Data Management (UDM). The steps for the authentication of a ABS are as follows:

Figure 2: Proposed ABS authentication flow with SSI blockchain built on top of 3GPP UAV authentication scheme.

- ① The ABS computes the Subscription Concealed Identifier (SUCI) by encrypting the Subscription Permanent Identifier (SUPI) with the GBS public key.
- ② The ABS sends the SUCI to Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF).
- ③ The AMF shares the SUCI with UDM.
- ④ UDM decrypts the SUCI and compares the SUPI with the BCN data.
- ⑤ If the SUPI is valid, a random value is generated by UDM and it is appended with SUCI (represented as XRES).
- ⑥ The UDM sends back to AMF the RAND and SUPI and registers SUCI, SUPI and XRES to SSI-BCN.

- ⑦ The AMF extracts the random value and shares it with the ABS and SSI-BCN.
- ⑧ The ABS appends the SUCI to a random value and sends it to the SSI-BCN (represented as XRES*).
- ⑨ The SSI-BCN verifies the identity of the ABS by checking ABS credentials and permissions on the system are correct,
- ⑩ Both GBS and ABS perform an authentication via the SSI-BCN system.
- ⑪ After SSI-BCN confirmation messages to AMF and GBS, the AMF begins to provide 3GPP service to the ABS.

In summary, the authentication of ABSs to provide 3GPP network services is accomplished with two phases with SSI-BCN framework. In the first phase, usual UE authentication process is followed between ABS and core network with the exception of inclusion of SSI-BCN. In the second step, a second authentication is performed between ABS control station and ABS.

3.6. Use Case: ABS handover between GBSs belonging to multiple operators

A concrete example of the application of the proposed BCN-based SSI architecture is for PPDR applications when ABS needs to handover between GBSs belonging to multiple operators. In this scenario, authenticating ABSs while protecting their privacy in a scalable and reliable way is a challenge, as a central authority is required to manage and identify the identities. Fig. 1 also presents a use case of PPDR for a multi-operator scenario. The proposed BCN-based SSI architecture can help ABSs to securely and efficiently identify themselves while sharing their information with other ABSs or relevant authorities (e.g., information and communication technologies authority or disaster and emergency management control authority). This potentially benefits the automation process of sharing ABSs between GBSs of multi- operators.

4. Experimental Analysis

4.1. Test Setup

In our test setup, the OpenStack platform is used. Two Virtual Machines (VMs) are created in OpenStack. The use of VMs in the OpenStack platform allows for the creation of isolated environments that mimic the network components involved in ABS authentication to enable the simulation of interactions between the ABS, GBS, AMF, and UDM as prescribed by 3GPP. A REpresentational State Transfer (REST) server is created to generate the appropriate requests to Hyperledger Indy. One of the virtual machines has a REST Application Programming Interface (API). The other VM has a DID system set up in a container-based structure. Hyperledger Indy is used for the DID blockchain in the test setup. A total of 8 GB RAM, 4 vCPUs, and 40 GB of disk space are reserved for the DID VM in Openstack. Implementing a DID system within container-based structures aligns with the need for secure and decentralized identity management, a critical aspect of the ABS authentication process. These containers simulate the identity issuance and verification procedures that ensure ABS integrity and trustworthiness within the network. During the Hyperledger Indy installation, the von network setup⁵ was performed on which container-based nodes

⁵VON Network, Available: <https://github.com/bcgov/von-network>, Online: March 2023.

will run. A total of four DID container nodes were created as DID issuers. A REST API is used to send requests from users to BCN. REST API is implemented using Flask framework. Calls to the BCN were made by implementing the DIDComm messaging protocol (s an asynchronous encrypted communication protocol developed as part of the Hyperledger Aries project⁶). The use of the DIDComm messaging protocol, as part of the Hyperledger Aries project, facilitates asynchronous and encrypted communication between network entities. This aligns with the secure communication requirements outlined by 3GPP during ABS authentication. In our assumed scenario, above DID implementation may be used to manage the credentials and identities of the BSs to ensure secure communication between the BSs and other nodes in the network.

4.2. Considered Metrics

We started requests from REST API for registration of users (credential offer) and for verification of registered user (credential presentation). In addition, we calculated the average connection establishment times and the average signing times of messages for the DIDComm protocol. Table 1 provides the average values of experimental DID implementation for credential operations after REST API calls to five endpoints for communication with DID blockchain system are performed.

The *average credential presentation time* measures the average amount of time it takes for verification process to occur, from the moment the user presents the credential to the verifier to the moment the verifier completes the verification process. This operation executes read and is represented by third and fourth steps in Fig. 1. The *average credential offer time* measures the average amount of time it takes for an issuer to generate and offer a credential in response to a user’s request. This includes the time it takes for the issuer to authenticate the user and check the validity of their request, as well as the time it takes to generate the credential and send it to the user. This operation executes write and is represented by first and second steps in Fig. 1.

Average DIDcomm connection creation time measures the amount of time it takes for two parties to establish a secure communication channel using the DIDcomm protocol. This includes the time it takes for each party to authenticate the other party’s identity, exchange DIDs and credentials, and negotiate the cryptographic parameters necessary for secure communication. According to our numerical results, this process takes the longest time in comparison to other metric time values. The *average DIDcomm connection signing time* measures the average amount of time it takes for two parties to sign a DIDcomm connection using digital signatures. This includes the time it takes for each party to verify the other party’s identity, generate and sign the necessary cryptographic keys, and negotiate the cryptographic parameters necessary for secure communication. Note that *Average DIDcomm connection creation time* and *average DIDcomm connection signing time* are necessary for any transactions to be on BCN. In other words, DIDcomm must be established first to compute metrics such as *average DIDcomm revoke credential time*, *average credential presentation time* and *average DIDcomm revoke credential time* values.

The *average DIDcomm revoke credential time* measures the average amount of time it takes for an issuer to revoke a verifiable credential and notify the relevant parties using the DIDcomm protocol. This includes the time it takes for the issuer to identify the need for revocation, generate and sign the revocation credential, and notify the relevant parties through a secure communication channel. This operation executes write and is represented by first step in Fig. 1. Note that revocation can only be executed by the issuer.

⁶Aries RFC 0005: DID Communication, Available: <https://bit.ly/3TKFUKG> , Online: March 2023.

4.3. Results and Discussions

As shown in Table 1, all KPIs described above are measured for three different scenarios with 50K, 75K, and 100K requests. These three cases, representing varying request volumes are likely chosen to provide a diverse range of scenarios (a moderate, heightened and high operational scale) that effectively illustrate the system’s behavior to capture different operational scales and potential challenges that might arise. The emphasis of this analysis is also on the depth of insights gained from the chosen cases. Challenges tackled include ensuring the resilience of the DID management system under moderate, high and extreme loads, verifying that cryptographic operations remain efficient and secure from moderate to high request volumes, and highlighting the system’s ability to uphold security and trust during demanding or peak usage.

In general, the results of the experiment indicate that as the number of requests increases, the performance of the DID management system degrades. However, the amount of increase in the number of requests is not directly proportional to increase in the average time values observed in KPIs. When comparing the average credential offer time across the three scenarios, we can observe an increase of 14.29% (from 525 milliseconds to 603 milliseconds) as the number of requests doubles (increases from 50K to 100K). The increase in average credential presentation time is even more pronounced, with a percentage increase of 18.18% (from 33 milliseconds to 39 milliseconds) between 50K and 100K requests. The average DIDcomm connection creation time and DIDcomm connection signing time also exhibit an increasing trend as the number of requests increases. The average DIDcomm connection creation time increases by 11.7% (from 659 milliseconds to 736 milliseconds) and the average DIDcomm connection signing time increases by 12.5% (from 64 milliseconds to 72 milliseconds) between 50K and 100K requests. The average revoke credential time for 50K requests is 212 milliseconds, while the average revoke credential time for 100K requests is 277 milliseconds, which represents an increase of 30.66%. The differences in performance across different request volumes indicate that the BCN-based SSI system needs to be resilient under varying loads to maintain acceptable levels of performance.

TABLE 1
AVERAGE VALUES OF EXPERIMENTAL DID IMPLEMENTATION FOR CREDENTIAL OPERATIONS WITH SECURITY ANALYSIS.

KPI	50K Requests	75K Requests	100K Requests	Security Analysis
Average credential presentation time (msec)	33	35	39	Fast
Average credential offer time (msec)	525	565	603	Moderate
Average DIDcomm connection creation time (msec)	659	681	736	Secure
Average DIDcomm signing time (msec)	64	68	72	Very Secure
Average DIDcomm revoke credential time (msec)	212	256	277	Secure

Furthermore, the credential presentation time and DIDcomm signing time are relatively fast, while the credential offer time and DIDcomm connection creation time are slower. The average

revoke credential time is also relatively fast, but it shows an unexpected increase of 20.75% compared to the 50k requests for 75K requests. In particular, compared to 50K requests, the credential presentation time and DIDcomm signing time have increased slightly, while the credential offer time and DIDcomm connection creation time have increased more significantly for 75K requests. For 100k requests, compared to the previous value for 75K requests, all KPIs have also shown an increase in their values. The credential presentation time has increased by 11.43%, the credential offer time has increased by 6.15%, the DIDcomm connection creation time has increased by 7.99%, the DIDcomm signing time has increased by 5.88%, and the revoke credential time has increased by an increase of 30.66%. Note that the percentage increase in revoke credential time gets higher with additional requests. This suggests that the performance of the system in handling revocation requests may be more affected by the number of requests than other operations such as credential presentation, offer, and DIDcomm connection creation and signing. The significant increase in the average revoke credential time highlights the challenges of efficiently processing revocation requests, which is critical to maintaining the security of the identity management system. In dynamic scenarios where ABS connect to different operators, ensuring timely revocation becomes even more important. Therefore, revoke credential time operation deserves special attention due to the more pronounced impact, as timely revocation is crucial for maintaining the integrity of identity management in PPDR scenarios. The observed increase in average DIDcomm connection creation time in our scenario implies that when secure and efficient communication is essential, optimizations or alternative strategies may be required to ensure timely secure communication channel establishments. This increase indicates that there may be delays in the authentication process that affect the overall efficiency of the system. This can be particularly critical for time-critical applications such as PPDR, where fast and reliable authentication and maintaining the confidentiality and integrity of the information exchanged during PPDR operations is crucial.

Note that read operations are faster than write operations considering above metrics as expected since in read operations only smart contracts are called. However, in all write operations, both smart contract calls and writing to BCN are executed. Considering that many ABSs can be simultaneously on the air, increasing the possibility of read operations to smart contract calls during network planning can be important for quick query responses. Another point to consider is that DIDcomm connection can slow down the system but is easy to apply considering its conformance to DID system. However, for fast secure connection, alternatively Transport Layer Security (TLS) can also be used with extra customization effort on DID system. Note that while the experimental results show some performance degradation under increased operating conditions, they also provide valuable insights for optimizing and fine-tuning the DID management system. Firstly, continuous monitoring is essential to ensure the resilience and efficiency of the system at different operating scales. Secondly, it highlights the need for continuous optimization and possible adaptation or fine-tuning to increased demand and underlines the dynamic nature of identity management in ABS-integrated networks. Thirdly, the trade-off between security and efficiency is also crucial to find the right balance so that the identity management system remains secure while efficiently handling authentication and communication in a dynamic environment. Therefore, these results on operational metrics can greatly contribute to a comprehensive understanding of system behavior and provide the basis for addressing the challenges associated with the increasing demand for identity management in ABS-integrated networks.

Security analysis: Table 1 also lists the security analysis of the experimental DID implementation which provides valuable insights into the robustness of the proposed solution. The average

time taken for credential presentation indicates a fast process, highlighting efficient identity verification without compromising security. Similarly, the average time for credential offer shows a moderate level of execution, reflecting a balanced approach to security and operational efficiency. The establishment of secure communication channels using DIDcomm consistently demonstrates a secure performance, maintaining a steadfast shield against potential threats across various request volumes. Moreover, the cryptographic signing time for message verification portrays very secure execution times, ensuring a high level of protection against unauthorized access or tampering. Lastly, the process of revoking credentials maintains secure execution times, underscoring the commitment to security even in scenarios where access needs to be invalidated. This comprehensive security analysis across credential operations and communication processes reaffirms the robustness and reliability of the proposed DID-based approach in meeting stringent security requirements.

Table 2 provides a breakdown of the status of 100,000 experimental DID operations. The majority of the operations, 98.83%, were successful without any errors. This high success rate is a sign of the overall robustness and reliability of the DID implementation and shows that it is able to handle a significant volume of operations effectively. However, a small percentage of the operations encountered errors. The most common error was an ‘‘Internal Server Error’’, which occurred in 0.853% of operations. This error was related to a failure in the REST API. This indicates that problems with the API infrastructure, which is crucial for system communication, need to be fixed to improve overall system stability. Another error, ‘‘Not Processable Entity’’, was related to credential issues and occurred in only 0.309% of operations. This underscores the importance of continuously refining credential management processes to reduce such errors. The error ‘‘Precondition Failed’’ was related to DiDComm and occurred in only 0.004% of operations. Although it is rare, it underlines how important it is to ensure the smooth functioning of the DiDComm components in order to guarantee a high success rate. The error ‘‘Not Allowed Method’’ was also related to DiDComm and occurred in only 0.001% of operations. Similar to the ‘‘Precondition Failed’’ error, it emphasises the need to pay close attention to the DiDComm processes. Overall, the percentage of errors was relatively low, with the majority of operations being successful. However, the errors that did occur were mostly related to technical issues with the system, highlighting the importance of continuous monitoring and maintenance to ensure the smooth operation of the system.

TABLE 2
VALUES OF EXPERIMENTAL DID IMPLEMENTATION FOR 100K OPERATION STATUS.

Status	Reason	Value	Percentage
Successful	-	98831	98,830 %
Internal Server Error	REST API Failure	854	0,853 %
Not Processable Entity	Credential Related	5	0,309 %
Precondition Failed	DiDComm Related	309	0,004 %
Not Allowed Method	DiDComm Related	2	0,001 %

5. Various Techniques Comparisons, Challenges & Future Directions

5.1. SSI-based vs. NFT-based Solutions

The concept of the digital asset was introduced with NFTs. Therefore, a solution based on NFT can also be used to store identity information in a BCN. For example, an NFT can be created for a

specific ABS and the NFT ownership can be assigned to the corresponding ABS. This can also be considered a similar structure to the SSI architecture. However, there are some fundamental differences between the SSI architecture and NFT within the BCN. First of all, NFTs is used to digitally sign a digital asset. SSI and NFT concepts can be compared as follows: With NFTs a user can show what he/she owns, while with SSI the digital identity can be proven. From this perspective, NFTs are mostly used for physical objects, such as artworks. However, for movable ABSs that are in constant communication with their environment, SSI-based authentication is required. Table 3 provides a comparison of BCN-based NFT and SSI technologies applied to an ABS-integrated network identification solution. **In terms of identity management**, NFT-based solutions often focus on tokenization and ownership representation. While this can be useful for asserting ownership, it may not fully address the intricacies of identity management and selective information sharing. **In terms of granularity of control**, NFTs are primarily designed for representing ownership or rights and may not inherently provide the same level of fine-grained control over identity attributes as SSI. **In terms of trust establishment**, NFTs may indeed represent ownership, but they may not provide the same level of trust establishment required for secure and accountable interactions in ABS-integrated networks as SSI. **In terms of interoperability and flexibility**, NFTs could excel at tokenizing assets, but they may lack the necessary flexibility to meet various identity and authentication requirements in ABS-integrated networks in comparison to SSI. **In terms of decentralized management**, NFTs inherently might not provide the same level of decentralized identity management and control as SSI, potentially introducing central points of control or reliance. Finally, **in terms of ecosystem collaboration**, while NFTs can facilitate the representation of ownership, they may not inherently foster the same level of ecosystem collaboration (e.g. between issuers, verifiers, and individuals (ABSs)) and verification processes as SSI. To summarise, the choice between SSI- and NFT-based solutions in the context of ABS-integrated networks depends on the specific requirements of each scenario. While NFTs may excel at tokenizing assets and representing ownership rights, SSI offers advantages in decentralized identity control, fine-grained attribute exchange, trust establishment, interoperability, and adaptability to dynamic network environments. With these considerations in mind, a more informed decision can be made to meet the security, privacy and operational requirements of ABS-integrated networks.

TABLE 3
COMPARISONS OF BCN-BASED NFT AND SSI TECHNOLOGIES FOR ABS-INTEGRATED
NETWORK IDENTITY MANAGEMENT PROBLEM.

Solution	Characteristics	Advantages	Disadvantages
NFT based Identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Allows tokenization of ABSs. — Used to certify ABS ownership. — Confer licensing rights for ABS usage. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Cannot be copied, substituted, or subdivided. — Contains a reference on blockchain for ABS. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Introduced in a ERC-721 standard format. — The ERC-1155 standard offers semi-fungibility for ABS classes. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Wide industry implementation experience. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Can be created by anybody. — Proving the ownership of a ABS but not the commercial usage rights. — Removes the transparency and traceability of ABS owner.
Self-Soverign Identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Establishes trust for interactions between ABS and GBSs. — Gives individual ABSs control over the information they use. — Digital ABS identities are managed in a decentralized manner. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Provides great flexibility for dynamically moving ABSs. — Presents an overall architecture with issuers and verifiers. — The class of the ABS can be indicated in the identity proof. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Lack of implementation experience in industry for DiDComm. — Unmature, but developing standardization aspects for mobile networks.

5.2. Challenges

Key Management: Since SSI management models hand over responsibility to users, key management is a major challenge in BCN-based SSI architectures.

Lack of Implementation and Standardization Details: The development of appropriate technologies and infrastructures to achieve the security and interoperability of such a BCN-based SSI architecture with clear guidelines and standards is still an ongoing study in the ecosystem. Note that identity verification processes need to be updated for each transaction. In a man-in-the-middle attack, the malicious user can obtain the DID belonging to a ABS user if the verification process is not carried out for every transaction. However, verifying the identity for each transaction has an impact on the transaction time.

Validation of New Identity Verifier: It is a challenge to select new verifiers and integrate them into the system. If a node needs to be added to the system, who gives this identity verifier node authority in the system? For example, when new countries are added to the EU, their ABS licence permitting institutions should also be included as a node in the system. As a solution to this challenge, the process of inclusion in the system can be carried out by the node that has the authority to record.

Interoperability for Secure Communication: Interoperability between different networks is a major challenge. Therefore, achieving seamless interoperability with the existing ABS infrastructure and other communication protocols could be a challenge. Difficulties in integrating the proposed SSI-BCN solution into existing ABS communication systems may affect compatibility. In the studies related to SSI, for secure communication between the user and the identity verifier, the implementation of the messaging protocol DID Communications (DIDComm) [24] is on the agenda. This protocol is adapted for DID messages. However, from a security point of view, the TLS protocol is now more widely used in the industry and knowledge of it is at a higher level. In this regard, the development of middleware between TLS and SSI blockchain could be a sufficient solution to provide DIDComm functionality.

Performance Issues of Blockchain Platforms: If the blockchain technologies currently in use are investigated, the Transactions per Second (TPS) values are around 3000 TPS even in the best cases. However, if it were necessary to use BCN when several ABSs need DID at the same time, this can lead to problems. For example, there are about 106 thousand 5G BSs in the EU [34]. As a workaround, messaging queuing services such as Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT), Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) can be used before data is transferred to blockchain networks. In this case, however, the need for real-time tasks may be affected. Another, still preliminary solution would be to prioritize ABSs according to their service types in DID proof processes. For this reason, an advanced blockchain platform with faster sharding capabilities should be created for such scenarios.

True negative rates: Our analysis has shown that the false alarm rate can be effectively minimized. However, this comes at the small price of an increased rate of true negative alarms, which is less problematic for our particular fake base station scenario.

Efficiency concerns with blockchain systems: While the SSI blockchain provides trust and security, it can lead to inefficiencies in terms of transaction processing speed and resource utilization. The proposed method could have a higher demand on resources such as computing power and storage space. Future experimentation on the use of the integrated system is required to mitigate longer transaction times and higher resource consumption processes during certain SSI operations that may impact the overall efficiency of the system the feasibility of deployment in resource-constrained environments.

Scalability concerns: As mentioned in the numerical results section, the performance of the proposed system in handling revocation requests seems to be affected by the number of requests rather

than other operations such as credential presentation or DIDcomm connection creation and signing. With a larger number of ABS entities, performance metrics may deteriorate. This may lead to scalability concerns with the current solution and require additional considerations such as distributed functions with acceptable consensus delays.

5.3. Future Directions

Post Quantum Cryptography (PQC) has emerged as a new security layer to protect against quantum computers, and must be adapted for telecommunications networks [35]. In particular, BCNs may suffer from quantum attacks during the block commit phase [36, 37]. Therefore, BCN-based SSI solutions need to be adapted to the evolving architectural and algorithmic developments in the post-quantum era. **SSI as a Service** can work in a robust and scalable way with the blockchain platform, which is actually based on a cloud-native architecture. This requires the underlying blockchain platform of SSI to be provided as a service. In this way, the roles of verifier and issuer can be provided as a service more quickly. **Homomorphic encryption** as a service can be added to a SSI system in the cloud [38] to ensure the necessary confidentiality of the executed transactions. **DIDComm Messaging** must support data formats other than JavaScript Object Notation (JSON), which is currently the only available format. In addition, the addition of forward and backward secrecy in DIDComm messages must be considered. **Open API** can actually open DID services to external environments and create an environment in which service providers for ABSs can be integrated. DIDComm integration does not have to be carried out individually by each service provider. Therefore, SSI can be easily accessed with REST API calls. This makes it easy to activate different services for ABSs.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, we conducted a comprehensive investigation of a BCN-based SSI platform specifically tailored for authentication and authorization in ABS-integrated networks for PPDR applications. We delved into the security properties of BCN-based SSI for ABSs, introduced the concept of cheating rates as a fundamental metric, and provided a comprehensive analysis of BCN-based SSI authentication. We also presented the architecture of the proposed platform and described its components, the dynamics of collaboration in identity management and the individual steps of interaction within ABS-integrated networks. We also performed extensive simulations to compute the average values of various KPIs (namely, average credential presentation time, average credential offer time, average DIDcomm connection creation time, average DIDcomm signing time, and average DIDcomm revoke credential time) related to credential operations in a DID management system for three different numbers of requests (50K, 75K, and 100K). We provided the values of different status codes that were encountered during 100K operations in the same DID management system. The majority of the operations (98.83%) were successful, while a small percentage encountered errors related to REST API failure or credential processing. At the end of the paper, we also compared SSI-based and NFT-based alternative solutions to enable authentication services for ABS-integrated networks and presented challenges and future directions of BCN-based SSI as an ABS identity management solution.

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References

- [1] Kim, Hyunbum and Ben-Othman, Jalel, Toward integrated virtual emotion system with AI applicability for secure CPS-enabled smart cities: AI-based research challenges and security issues, *IEEE Network* 34 (3) (2020) 30–36.
- [2] B. Goswami, H. Choudhury, A blockchain-based authentication scheme for 5G-enabled IoT, *Journal of Network and Systems Management* 30 (4) (2022) 1–33.
- [3] K. Albalawi, M. M. A. Azim, Cloud-based IoT device authentication scheme using blockchain, in: 2019 IEEE Global Conference on Internet of Things (GCIoT), IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–7.
- [4] A. Preukschat, D. Reed, *Self-sovereign identity*, Manning Publications, 2021.
- [5] Katharina Koerner, *Self-sovereign identity as future privacy by design solution in digital identity?*, White Paper Available: <https://bit.ly/3UFsM8s>, [Online; accessed December-2022].
- [6] M. S. Alkathairi, S. Saleem, M. A. Alqarni, A. O. Aseeri, S. H. Chauhdary, Y. Zhuang, A lightweight authentication scheme for a network of unmanned aerial vehicles (uavs) by using physical unclonable functions, *Electronics* 11 (18) (2022) 2921.
- [7] M. Nikooghadam, H. Amintoosi, S. H. Islam, M. F. Moghadam, A provably secure and lightweight authentication scheme for internet of drones for smart city surveillance, *Journal of Systems Architecture* 115 (2021) 101955.
- [8] F. Neto, J. Granjal, V. Pereira, A survey on security approaches on PPDR systems towards 5G and beyond, *IEEE Access*.
- [9] Kim, Hyunbum and Ben-Othman, Jalel and Hwang, Kwang-il and Choi, Byoungjo, Intelligent aerial-ground surveillance and epidemic prevention with discriminative public and private services, *IEEE Network* 36 (3) (2022) 40–46.
- [10] E. Zeydan, et al., Blockchain-based service orchestration for 5G vertical industries in multi-cloud environment, *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management* (2022) 1–1doi:10.1109/TNSM.2022.3194078.
- [11] L. Ferranti, et al., Skycell: A prototyping platform for 5G aerial base stations, in: 2020 IEEE Int. Symposium on “A World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks”(WoWMoM), IEEE, 2020, pp. 329–334.
- [12] S. S. Arslan, R. Jurdak, J. Jelitto, B. Krishnamachari, *Advancements in distributed ledger technology for internet of things* (2020).
- [13] H. Wang, J. Zhang, Blockchain based data integrity verification for large-scale iot data, *IEEE Access* 7 (2019) 164996–165006.
- [14] P. K. Nakarmi, M. A. Ersoy, E. U. Soykan, K. Norrman, Murat: Multi-rat false base station detector, arXiv preprint arXiv:2102.08780.
- [15] L. Karacay, Z. Bilgin, A. B. Gündüz, P. Comak, E. Tomur, E. U. Soykan, U. Gülen, F. Karakoc, A network-based positioning method to locate false base stations, *IEEE Access* 9 (2021) 111368–111382.
- [16] P. K. Nakarmi, et al., Detecting false base stations in mobile networks, *Ericsson Blog*, online: <https://bit.ly/40gizD4>, Available: March 2023. (2023).
- [17] M. Shuaib, N. H. Hassan, S. Usman, S. Alam, S. Bhatia, A. Mashat, A. Kumar, M. Kumar, Self-sovereign identity solution for blockchain-based land registry system: a comparison, *Mobile Information Systems* 2022 (2022) 1–17.
- [18] M. R. Ahmed, A. M. Islam, S. Shatabda, S. Islam, Blockchain-based identity management system and self-sovereign identity ecosystem: A comprehensive survey, *IEEE Access* 10 (2022) 113436–113481.
- [19] E. Zeydan, J. Mangués, S. S. Arslan, Y. Turk, Blockchain-based self-sovereign identity for routing in inter-domain networks, *IEEE Communications Magazine*.
- [20] E. Zeydan, J. Mangués, S. S. Arslan, Y. Turk, Self-sovereign identity management for hierarchical federated learning in vehicular networks, in: 2023 IEEE 24th International Conference on High Performance Switching and Routing (HPSR), IEEE, 2023, pp. 191–196.
- [21] E. Zeydan, J. Mangués, S. Arslan, Y. Turk, Blockchain-based self-sovereign identity solution for vehicular networks, in: 2023 19th International Conference on the Design of Reliable Communication Networks (DRCN), IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–7.
- [22] G. Kondova, J. Erbguth, Self-sovereign identity on public blockchains and the GDPR, in: *Proceedings of the 35th Annual ACM Symposium on Applied Computing*, 2020, pp. 342–345.
- [23] World Wide Web Consortium, *Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) v1.0*, Core architecture, data model, and representations, <https://www.w3.org/TR/did-core/> Online accessed: March 2023 (2022).

- [24] Identity Foundation, Didcomm messaging v2.x, <https://identity.foundation/didcomm-messaging/spec/> Online accessed: March 2023 (2023).
- [25] D. Rathee, G. V. Policharla, T. Xie, R. Cottone, D. Song, Zebra: Anonymous credentials with practical on-chain verification and applications to KYC in DeFi, Cryptology ePrint Archive.
- [26] Q. Stokkink, J. Pouwelse, Deployment of a blockchain-based self-sovereign identity, in: 2018 IEEE international conference on Internet of Things (iThings) and IEEE green computing and communications (GreenCom) and IEEE cyber, physical and social computing (CPSCom) and IEEE smart data (SmartData), IEEE, 2018, pp. 1336–1342.
- [27] T. Leinmüller, C. Maihöfer, E. Schoch, F. Kargl, Improved security in geographic ad hoc routing through autonomous position verification, in: Proceedings of the 3rd international workshop on Vehicular ad hoc networks, 2006, pp. 57–66.
- [28] M. Lichtman, R. P. Jover, M. Labib, R. Rao, V. Marojevic, J. H. Reed, Lte/lte-a jamming, spoofing, and sniffing: threat assessment and mitigation, IEEE Communications Magazine 54 (4) (2016) 54–61.
- [29] K.-W. Huang, H.-M. Wang, Identifying the fake base station: A location based approach, IEEE Communications Letters 22 (8) (2018) 1604–1607.
- [30] M. S. Ferdous, et al., In search of self-sovereign identity leveraging blockchain technology, IEEE Access 7 (2019) 103059–103079.
- [31] G. Zyskind, et al., Enigma: Decentralized computation platform with guaranteed privacy, arXiv preprint arXiv:1506.03471.
- [32] 3GPP Standard, 3GPP technical specification group services and system aspects; study on security aspects of unmanned aerial systems (UAS), TS 33.854 V0.6.0.
- [33] Y. Aydin, G. K. Kurt, E. Ozdemir, H. Yanikomeroglu, Authentication and handover challenges and methods for drone swarms, IEEE Journal of Radio Frequency Identification 6 (2022) 220–228.
- [34] National 5G Observatory (on5g), 5G commercial networks, present throughout the European Union, except Portugal and Lithuania, <https://on5g.es/en/analysis/> Online accessed: March 2023 (2021).
- [35] E. Zeydan, Y. Turk, B. Aksoy, S. B. Ozturk, Recent advances in post-quantum cryptography for networks: A survey, in: 2022 Seventh Int. Conf. on Mobile And Secure Services (MobiSecServ), 2022, pp. 1–8. doi:10.1109/MobiSecServ50855.2022.9727214.
- [36] E. Zeydan, et al., Post-quantum blockchain-based data sharing for IoT service providers, IEEE Internet of Things Magazine 5 (2) (2022) 96–101.
- [37] E. Zeydan, et al., Post-quantum blockchain-based secure service orchestration in multi-cloud networks, IEEE Access (early access).
- [38] M. Kang, V. Lemieux, A decentralized identity-based blockchain solution for privacy-preserving licensing of individual-controlled data to prevent unauthorized secondary data usage, Ledger 6.